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TEACHING QUALITY MANAGEMENT PERCEPTIONS AND EMPLOYABILITY AMONG GRADUATES OF SINO- FOREIGN COOPERATIVE EDUCATION IN FUJIAN, CHINA

Denggui Huang¹, Peng-Fei, Chen^{2*} and Huan Cao³

¹Dhurakij Pundit University, Jimei University Overseas Education College, 66140073@dpu.ac.th

²Dhurakij Pundit University, Email: blissfulalice@gmail.com

³Dhurakij Pundit University, caoh1516@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: Peng-Fei, Chen

(blissfulalice@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

This research is based on the Internationalisation Process Orientation Theory of Knight (2015) in order to determine how teaching quality management perception influences the employability of graduates of Fujian Province's "4+0" Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes, while assessing gender and major background differences. A total of 309 valid responses were collected. The results indicated that graduates' teaching quality management perception scores generally remain at a moderate-to-high level (M=3.993, SD=.584), with a significantly higher employability performance (M=4.451, SD=.511). While no significant differences were found in the teaching quality management perception of genders or majors, there was a significant disparity between the employability of genders. The results of a correlation analysis revealed that and teaching quality management perception remained a significant positive predictor of employability. This study provides empirical evidence and policy insights for optimising teaching quality management and cultivating internationalised talents in Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes.

KEYWORDS: Cooperative Teaching, Perceived Teaching Quality, Educational Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Transnational higher education has expanded rapidly over the past two decades to become one of the most important features of the global higher education system (De Wit & Altbach, 2020). In many countries, this type of higher education is regarded as an important strategic tool that has enhanced the level of human capital, introduced advanced educational concepts and practices, and strengthened national competitiveness (Knight, 2015). For example, it has been formally incorporated into the national education development agenda in China, with policies that explicitly encourage the introduction of foreign high-quality educational resources (Sun, 2022). Against this backdrop, Sino-foreign cooperative education has developed rapidly, as an important form of transnational higher education that provides students with a practical path to acquire international learning experience without having to leave the country. However, although existing researchers emphasise the positive role of Sino-foreign cooperative education in promoting students' ability to develop comprehensively (Xiao, 2024), policy frameworks, institutional governance and students' learning experience are likely to be their main focus (McKay & Robson, 2023), while the number of empirical studies of the effect of teaching quality management on graduates' employability remains limited (Di et al., 2022). Many researchers adopt a simplified input-output analytical perspective to directly examine the relationship between the investment in education and students' employment outcomes, while neglecting the complexity of the educational process and the key role of students' subjective experience (Strom & Viesca, 2023). Rather than teaching management being naturally transformed into graduates' employment ability, it depends on their perception of teaching quality management.

Students' perception of quality teaching management, which is often defined as their comprehensive evaluation of the course organisation, instructional support and quality assurance processes, is recognised as a key determinant of students' learning engagement and development of competency (Rosa et al., 2012). Researchers have demonstrated that effective teaching management can improve graduates' employability by optimising the structure of the curriculum, aligning pedagogical approaches with learning outcomes, and bridging the gap between academic achievements and the labour market demands (Biggs et al., 2022). However, empirical evidence of a correlation between students'

perception of teaching management quality and graduates' employability remains limited in Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes.

Furthermore, students' demographic characteristics and academic backgrounds may have a significant effect on their teaching experience and employment outcomes. It has been indicated by researchers that gender differences are evident in students' evaluation of teaching quality and management, with female students generally being more sensitive to teaching services (Dicker et al., 2017). Additionally, students from different academic backgrounds exhibit variations in the structure and level of employability, with distinctive career development paths and professional orientations (Winberg et al., 2020). However, few researchers have systematically examined the effect of students' gender and academic background on the relationship between their perception of teaching management and employability in cross-border or Sino-foreign cooperative educational contexts.

As a coastal province with open policies, Fujian has witnessed a steady increase in the number of annual Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes, with the 4+0 model holding a prominent position in its higher education institutions (Li, 2021). The province's 4+0 cooperative education programmes have produced a total of 18 graduating cohorts consisting of approximately 6,600 students, making them ideal research subjects in this context. These programmes not only address the practical needs of regional education development, but they also help to fill the gap in graduate career development research under specific training models.

The present study examines graduates from the 4+0 cooperative education programme in Fujian Provinces, with a focus on their employability. Graduates' perception of the influence of teaching management on their employability was examined, as well as different gender and academic backgrounds in relevant variables. The aim of this part of the research was to deepen the understanding of the mechanisms of teaching management in Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes by providing empirical evidence to enhance teaching quality management and graduates' competitiveness in terms of employability. Questionnaire surveys were used and the results subjected to descriptive statistics, a variance analysis and a regression analysis. Based on the findings, conclusions and recommendations are proposed to improve the quality of Sino-foreign cooperative education and cultivate talents who are internationally competent.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. *Knight's Internationalisation Theory*

2.1.1. *Concept*

Theoretically, Knight (2004, 2015) has delineated the essence of the internationalisation of higher education based on three dimensions, namely, international, cross-cultural and global. The international dimension emphasises transnational collaboration and the exchange of knowledge, the cross-cultural dimension is focused on learning and communication in multicultural environments, while the global dimension highlights global responsibility and sustainable development (Knight, 2004, 2015). These dimensions are not isolated, but they interactively shape university governance structures, curricula and teaching practices, continuously driving the integration of internationalisation into the higher education system. Knight (2015) further emphasises that, instead of only pursuing scale expansion or market-driven goals, internationalisation should enhance educational quality and students' development outcomes (Guo et al., 2022; Lazari & Matsoukas, 2025).

2.1.2. *International Quality Management of Knight's Theory Teaching*

It is emphasised in Knight's Internationalisation Theory that the implementation of internationalisation should not be confined to cross-border mobility; instead, it should be systematically integrated into core components like the curriculum, teaching, research and governance (Knight, 2004, 2015). In this context, the management of teaching quality not only involves the curriculum design, instructional delivery, assessment feedback, and continuous improvement, but it also determines whether international education goals can be effectively translated into students' development outcomes. Hence, it is recognised as a critical mechanism for ensuring the effectiveness of internationalisation (Guo et al., 2022; Lazari & Matsoukas, 2025). Knight (2015) explicitly states that internationalisation can genuinely enhance students' competencies and that educational value can only be recognised when it is supported by high-quality teaching and effective management. It is also indicated in related research that the systematic management of teaching quality can strengthen curriculum coherence and practical orientation, improve students' comprehensive abilities and readiness for a career, thereby having a direct impact on graduates' employability (Biggs et al., 2022).

2.1.3. *Sino-Foreign Cooperative Education and Employability Development in the Context of China*

Sino-foreign cooperative education is a significant practice of internationalisation in higher education in China, particularly the 4+0 training model, which is widely regarded as a typical case of localisation of internationalisation under the Knight framework (Guo et al., 2022; Junyi & Zainudin, 2024). This model integrates international and global dimensions into the local teaching system without relying on cross-border student mobility by introducing foreign curricula, implementing bilingual or full English instruction and conducting collaborative teaching and quality assessment by a Sino-foreign faculty (Guo et al., 2022). Teaching quality management fosters the development of students' professional competencies, general skills and vocational literacy based on process control, learning support and feedback mechanisms. This ensures that the integration between foreign curricula and the local education system is effective, as well as prevents curriculum fragmentation and standardisation imbalances (Wahab et al., 2025). Under the 4+0 model, teaching quality management not only serves as an institutional foundation for project implementation, but it also has a direct impact on the formation and enhancement of graduates' employability (Hu & Cheung, 2021; Mittelmeier et al., 2020).

2.2. *Perception Of Teaching Quality Management (TQMP)*

Teaching quality management is generally defined in current research as a systematic process, whereby higher education institutions implement institutional policies, standard procedures and dynamic improvement mechanisms in order to plan, execute, monitor, and optimise teaching processes and outcomes (Chen et al., 2026; Guo et al., 2022). Teaching quality management is a cyclical and systematic process that requires the integration of preliminary planning, process control and post-action feedback (Wahab et al., 2025). Hence, it is typically categorised into three interconnected core dimensions, namely quality monitoring, evaluation feedback and continuous improvement. Quality monitoring specifically ensures that teaching operations are standardised, that evaluation feedback is focused on collecting and diagnosing teaching effectiveness data, and that continuous improvement is centred on optimising and innovating teaching practices based on assessment

results (Guo *et al.*, 2022). This framework highlights the dynamic cyclical nature of the management of teaching quality, which is closely aligned with Knight's (2015) emphasis on internationalised process orientation and systematic approaches.

In the international education context, the function of TQM is not only as an institutional framework, but also as a practical process based on students' experience. Their subjective evaluation of TQM, known as Teaching Quality Management Perception (TQMP), reflects a comprehensive understanding of institutional management practices in areas such as standard-setting, process monitoring, assessment feedback and continuous improvement. This perception serves as a critical dimension for measuring the quality of international education and learning experience (Abbas *et al.*, 2024). Researchers have indicated that students' TQMP is influenced by factors that include the transparency of the institution, faculty support, feedback mechanisms and interaction with the learning environment, which have a further impact on their learning engagement, motivation to achieve and developmental outcomes (Zhang & Tu, 2024). Hence, TQMP is defined in this study as students' subjective perception and evaluation of the quality assurance activities implemented by institutions in international teaching processes, emphasising its subjective, interactive and process-orientated nature.

2.3. *Employability*

2.3.1. *Definition*

In the context of international higher education, employability exhibits structural characteristics that are multidimensional. Building on prior research, Chen *et al.* (2023) propose that employability can be categorised into three dimensions, namely professional skills, international competitiveness and potential career development. International competitiveness emphasises individuals' adaptability and communication skills in cross-cultural, multilingual and pluralistic value environments, where they serve as a critical foundation for graduates to achieve career mobility and advantages in a globalised context (Knight, 2015). The potential for career development is focused on individuals' capacity for continuous learning, proactive planning and self-renewal, reflecting their ability to maintain long-term competitiveness in rapidly changing professional environments (Akkermans *et al.*, 2024). From an international education perspective, Knight (2015) argues that employability is a significant extension of higher education outcomes, which should be

systematically cultivated by the internationalisation of the curriculum, teaching quality management and cross-cultural learning experience. This process-orientated approach highlights that employability is not directly generated by single teaching inputs, but is gradually formed by the combined effects of teaching quality management, curriculum design and learning experience. Employability becomes more complex in Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes, particularly the 4+0 model, due to its international orientation. High-quality teaching quality management provides crucial support for the development of students' employability based on the internationalisation of the curriculum and optimised teaching processes (Chen *et al.*, 2023).

In line with prior research, employability in this study is defined as a comprehensive integration of the knowledge, skills, attitudes and personal traits graduates require to successfully obtain, maintain and develop a career. Specifically, it encompasses the three dimensions of professional skills, international competitiveness and the potential to develop a career (Chen *et al.*, 2023). This definition is aligned with the objectives to cultivate talent in Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes and it provides a clear theoretical foundation for analysing the relationship between perceived teaching quality management and graduates' employability.

2.4. *Hypotheses*

Researchers have indicated that demographic variables such as gender and academic background affect students' perception of educational processes and their development outcomes (Zhang, 2023). Teachers of quality management perception confirm that gender differences are a significant factor that affects students' educational evaluation (Kwok & Potter, 2022). It has been shown in studies that female students typically exhibit higher sensitivity to feedback quality, classroom interaction, and learning support during the teaching process, often providing a more detailed evaluations of teaching quality management. In contrast, male students tend to focus more on elements of quality that are related to the course objectives, evaluation criteria, and outcome-orientated assessments (Kwok & Potter, 2022; Wahab *et al.*, 2025). These differences reflect distinctive cognitive orientations and quality expectations shaped by gender socialisation (Li, 2021).

Researchers have indicated that students in applied and practice-orientated fields (e.g., business and engineering) prioritise the direct impact of quality management on learning outcomes and professional skills, while those in theoretical

disciplines or humanities/social sciences focus more on feedback mechanisms and the coherence of learning experiences (Kember & Leung, 2011). This reveals that students' professional backgrounds not only shape their perceived priorities, but also create substantial differences in the perception of quality based on various learning contexts and teaching methodologies.

The teaching process in Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes (4+0) exhibits pronounced internationalisation and institutional complexity. Students from diverse backgrounds may demonstrate more pronounced differences in their perception of teaching quality management (Kunze & Rutherford, 2022). Given the challenges posed by curriculum systems, evaluation methods and instructional languages, students' gender and academic background may influence their assessment of the effectiveness of teaching quality management, which, in turn, influences their career development (Wahab et al., 2025). Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed;

H1: There are significant differences of gender in TQMP among graduates.

H2: There are significant differences of professional fields in TQMP among graduates.

Gender and professional background are widely recognised as significant individual variables that affect college students' employment capability. Employment capability not only reflects the accumulation of individuals' knowledge and skills, but is also the result of the combined effect of multiple factors, which include social gender roles, disciplinary culture and the choice of career path (Tomlinson et al., 2022).

Gender disparities in employability reveal distinctive advantages between men and women. It is demonstrated in empirical studies that women excel in soft skills, such as communication, coordination, interpersonal dynamics and emotional regulation, while men demonstrate a stronger performance in hard skills, such as logical analysis, technical operations and problem-solving (Dominic & Fulgence, 2019). These differences are reflected in both individual traits and societal expectations of gender roles (Clarke, 2018). Women's strengths of interpersonal sensitivity and cultural adaptation are amplified further in international education environments, in which teamwork and cross-cultural interaction are valued. However, career development opportunities are still constrained to some extent by gender-based structural inequalities (Wahab et al., 2025).

In terms of professional background, the type-

specific characteristics of students' employability are shaped by knowledge paradigms, curriculum structures and teaching models of different disciplines. Researchers have reported that STEM majors typically possess strong analytical reasoning and technical application skills, which are better aligned with the demands of technology-orientated positions, whereas humanities, social sciences and management majors excel in communication skills, innovative thinking and cross-cultural collaboration, which often demonstrate more flexible career development paths (Chen et al., 2023; Wahab et al., 2025). Under the framework of Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes, professional characteristics also interact with international curriculum systems and teaching models, causing structural differences in the competitiveness of students from different disciplines in the global job market (Lázár et al., 2024). Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed;

H3: There are significant differences of genders in employability among graduates.

H4: There are significant differences of professional fields in employability among graduates.

TQMP serves as the cornerstone of educational quality assurance systems. Its purpose extends beyond standardising teaching processes to driving educational outcomes and students' development based on continual optimisation and reflective improvement (Wahab et al., 2025). According to Knight's (2015) Internationalisation Process Theory, the internationalisation of higher education is not a static goal, but rather a cyclical "strategy-execution-feedback-improvement" process. TQMP acts as the critical mechanism that sustains this cycle, as it ensures the closed-loop operation of educational activities by implementing scientific quality monitoring systems, effective evaluation feedback mechanisms and systematic continuous improvement processes. This translates into enhanced learning outcomes and student-level employability (Knight, 2015). An extensive amount of empirical research has demonstrated that a robust TQMP system not only directly boosts students' learning engagement and academic achievement, but indirectly enhances graduates' employability based on the learning process (Asanov et al., 2024; Roszkowski, 2023).

The international dimension of TQMP is particularly crucial in the context of Sino-Foreign Cooperative Education (SFCE), when a teaching management system of a high standard can facilitate collaboration between Chinese and foreign teachers

in terms of curriculum design, teaching evaluation and quality monitoring, thereby transforming international teaching resources into students' globally competitive capabilities (Lázár *et al.*, 2024; Chen *et al.*, 2023). However, the effectiveness of TQMP varies across educational institutions. Some researchers have found that the institutionalisation level of quality assurance mechanisms, the quality of professional teacher training and students' participation have a significant impact on its ultimate outcomes (Lim *et al.*, 2019). Knight (2015) theorises that TQMP can only truly be a sustainable force for students' development when quality management processes achieve "cultural internalisation" and all members share the same belief about educational quality and the formation of reflective practices.

In summary, teaching quality management is not only a technical mechanism that ensures educational operations, but is also an intrinsic driver for enhancing employability. TQMP can promote the growth of students' employability by constructing quality culture and continuous improvement processes from an international perspective, strengthening graduates' ability to compete in the global labour market. Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed;

H5: The TQMP of graduates has a positive predictive effect on their employability.

3. METHODS

3.1. Participants

A total of 309 valid questionnaires were collected. There were 158 male graduates (51.133%) and 151 female graduates (48.867%). In terms of academic disciplines, Business Administration graduates (15,449.838%) and International Accounting graduate (15,550.162%) were almost equally represented.

3.2. Instruments Used in the Study

3.2.1. Perception Scale of Teaching Quality Management

The Student Perceptions of Higher Education Quality Assurance (SPHEQ) scale, which was developed by Ta *et al.* (2023), was used in this study. This scale is comprised of 4 core dimensions with 60 items, including the quality policy and quality assurance model awareness dimension (14 items), the quality assurance objectives and focus perception dimension (14 items), the quality assurance process and tools engagement dimension (21 items), and the quality assurance survey frequency and effect perception dimension (11 items). The scale

demonstrates both international quality assurance framework compatibility and local adaptability, achieving 87% content validity and providing a reliable measurement foundation for related empirical research.

3.2.2. Graduate Employability Scale

The Future Employment Competency Scale developed by Chen *et al.* (2023) was adopted for use in this study to assess college students' comprehensive abilities in terms of knowledge, skills, personality and career development. The scale consists of 28 items and uses a Likert five-point scale (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree), with an overall Cronbach's Alpha of .974. The Cronbach's Alphas for the four dimensions range from .917 to .940. The structural validity (CFI=.936, TLI=.921, RMSEA=.046) is excellent, indicating a stable and reliable theoretical structure. The researcher further validated the cross-context applicability of the scale across different regions and schools based on multi-sample testing, and revealed high reliability, validity and cultural adaptability (Chen *et al.*, 2023). In summary, the scale developed by Chen *et al.* (2023) fully reflects the educational and employment characteristics of Chinese college students and is suitable for the systematic measurement of college students' employment competencies in the context of Sino-foreign cooperative education and international education.

3.3. Procedure

This study is focused on students who enrolled in the 4+0 independent enrolment programme of Sino-foreign cooperative education in China's Fujian Province. These programmes involve full-time institutions and projects at the undergraduate level or above, excluding non-degree education and vocational education programmes. A stratified random sampling method was employed for the parent population (Lohr, 2019), whereby the population was divided into two strata—Business Administration and International Accounting—and equal numbers of participants ((1:1 sampling ratio) were randomly selected from each stratum to ensure representativeness. Before data collection, permission was obtained from Dhurakij Pundit Universitu (Decision No: DPU_BSH 2611/2568).

3.4. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, independent samples t-tests, Pearson's correlation and a regression analysis were employed using a questionnaire survey via SPSS version with 309 valid responses.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Analysis Of Differences

4.1.1. Gender

An independent samples t-test was utilised in this study to analyse the differences in the teaching quality management perception and employability of graduates of different genders. As shown in Table 1, the results of the analysis revealed no significant differences in genders’ perception of teaching quality

management ($t=.941, p=.348$), which indicated that male and female graduates have essentially the same overall perception of educational quality management. This result does not support H1.

There were significant differences in employability between graduates of different genders ($t=4.458, p<.001$). Based on the comparative results of the difference analysis, the employability of male graduates ($M=4.573, SD=0.442$) was significantly higher than that of female graduates ($M=4.321, SD=0.546$), thereby supporting H3.

Table 1: Analysis of Differences Between Genders in Various Variables

Variables	M (SD)		t	p	Analysis of variance
	Male (n=158)	Female (n=151)			
TQMP	4.023 (0.639)	3.961 (0.512)	0.941	.348	-
Employability	4.573 (0.442)	4.321 (0.546)	4.458	.000	Male>Female

4.1.2. Professional Fields

The result shows that there were no significant differences in the perception of teaching quality management of business administration graduates and international accounting majors ($t=.124, p=.902$), nor was there a significant difference in employability ($t=1.178, p=.240$), as shown in Table 2. These results do not support H2 and H4. The Sino-

foreign cooperative education programmes of China and Fujian Province universities show different perceptions of teaching quality management and employability among graduates with different professional backgrounds. These results indicate that graduates with different professional backgrounds generally exhibit consistent levels in their perception of teaching quality management and employability.

Table 2: Analysis of Differences of Professional Fields.

variable	M (SD)		t	p
	Business Administration (n=154)	International Accounting (n=155)		
Perception of Teaching Quality Management	3.997 (0.581)	3.989 (0.589)	0.124	.902
Employment	4.485 (0.456)	4.416 (0.560)	1.178	.240

4.2. Correlation

Pearson’s correlation analysis was utilised in this study to examine the relationship between graduates’ perceived teaching quality management and their employability. A significant positive correlation ($r=0.324, p<.001$) was illustrated between these two variables, providing a solid statistical foundation for a subsequent regression analysis.

($R^2=.159, Adjusted R^2=.151$), with the regression model being statistically significant ($F=19.273, p<.001$).

It was revealed by a further analysis of standardised regression coefficients that the perception of teaching quality management has a significantly stronger predictive effect on employability than the control variables of gender and major.

4.3. Regression

As shown in Table 3, after controlling for the variables of gender and professional background, their perception of teaching quality management was found to significantly predict graduates’ employability ($\beta=.312, p<.001$), indicating that a higher perception of teaching quality management is correlated with stronger employability. The overall model demonstrates acceptable explanatory power

Notably, gender was also revealed to have a significant and predictive effect on employability ($\beta=-.230, p<.001$), while major (international accounting versus business administration) had no significant predictive effect ($p>.050$). In conclusion, the perception of teaching quality management is an important predictor of the employability of graduates from Sino-foreign cooperative education programmes in universities in Fujian Province, China. H5 was supported.

Table 3: Regression Analysis.

	B	SE	β	t	p
constant	.235	.206	-	17.239	.000
female	-.230	.054	-.225	-4.254	.000
international accounting	-.039	.054	-.038	-0.717	.474
TQMP	.273	.046	.312	5.936	.000
R ²	.159				
Adj. R ²	.151				
F	F (308) =19.273, p=.000				

5. DISCUSSION

The results of both correlation and regression analyses demonstrated a significant positive correlation between graduations' perception of teaching quality management and their employability ($r=.324$, $p<.001$). After controlling for gender and major, perceived teaching quality management remained a significant positive predictor of employability ($\beta=.312$, $p<.001$), with the model explanatory power reaching an acceptable level (Adj. $R^2=.151$). This indicates that teaching quality management is not merely an institutional arrangement in the context of 4+0 Sino-foreign cooperative education, but it can be transformed into a higher self-evaluation of employability and stronger preparedness for a career by graduates' learning experience and experience of quality. This finding can be explained by Knight's process-orientated perspective, which is that internationalisation is not just about structurally introducing foreign resources, but it requires a quality closed-loop system of execution, feedback and improvement to continuously optimise courses, teaching and support systems during operation. Graduates' positive perception of clear quality objectives, focus on quality, evaluation participation, and effectiveness of quality improvement suggest they are more likely to acquire explicit learning expectations, visible feedback mechanisms, and stable learning support during their studies, thereby promoting the accumulation of professional learning, vocational literacy and career development capabilities. This result is also aligned with the conclusions of existing researchers, who have associated teaching management with competency output, indicating that systematic quality management enhances course coherence and practice orientation, which then strengthens students' career preparedness (Biggs *et al.*, 2022).

According to the results of the differences test, there were no significant gender differences in graduates' perception of teaching quality management ($p>.050$), but some significant

differences did exist in their self-rated employability, with the scores of male graduates significantly higher than those of their female counterparts ($t=4.458$, $p<.001$). These findings indicate that, while the perceived levels of school quality governance and teaching support remained generally consistent between genders in the same cooperative education programme, there were gender differences in self-evaluations of employability. Some possible explanations for these findings are that, firstly, the employability scale incorporates dimensions such as career confidence, career planning and psychological traits, which may be affected by gendered social expectations, differences in occupational opportunity structures and variations in self-efficacy, leading to systematic discrepancies in self-assessment levels. Secondly, women may be more sensitive to external opportunity constraints or perceived differences in career rewards when searching for jobs, resulting in more conservative self-evaluations. This finding is aligned with existing discussions of structural gender differences in employability and the labour market.

No significant differences were observed between the perception of teaching quality management and employment competencies of graduates of the two majors. The reasons for this are twofold: Firstly, students of both majors share an internationalised curriculum with a similar structure, teaching language environment and mechanism to ensure quality assurance, resulting in consistent student quality governance experience. Secondly, the training processes and employment support resources in the 4+0 programme are likely to be homogenised; therefore, there are insufficient professional differences to create significant competency differentiation.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The research establishes a competency-orientated framework to reform the frontline curriculum. Researchers have indicated that resource introduction alone cannot automatically translate

into students' competitiveness in the workplace. Therefore, an improvement pathway for teaching innovation is proposed in this study, which consists of shifting the curriculum design from language input to higher-order thinking output. Project-based learning (PBL) and peer collaboration mechanisms are vigorously recommended for implementation in imported courses in order to address the incompatibility of imported textbooks in Fujian's cultural context. This will not only enhance students' cross-cultural adaptability, but will also effectively improve their problem-solving capabilities. Despite these contributions, this study is subject to several methodological constraints. Specifically, the cross-sectional research design limits the ability to infer causal relationships, and the reliance on self-reported measures of employability may introduce response bias. These limitations should be addressed in future research through longitudinal designs and the incorporation of objective employability indicators.

7. PRACTICALLY IMPLICATION

Practically, it is demonstrated by the empirical results that the perception of teaching intelligence management has stable explanatory power over graduates' employability in the typical localised internationalisation context of 4+0 Sino-foreign cooperative education. This provides a data compass for university administrators to make quality decisions. At this critical juncture, where cross-border education shifts from scale expansion to connotative development, universities should utilise empirical results to adjust resource allocation

priorities. The focus should transition from hard indicators like foreign faculty ratios to soft indicators, such as monitoring cross-cultural interaction frequency and assessing the adaption of curriculum localisation. This management approach driven by data helps to precisely identify efficiency gaps in teaching processes, thereby significantly improving the input-output ratio and operational efficiency of Sino-foreign cooperative education (Bordogna, 2020).

8. CONCLUSION

Theoretical contribution: Teaching quality management is transformed in this study from institutional input into a perceptible process at the student level, thereby explaining differences in employability. It is emphasised that the effectiveness of quality governance depends on whether it is experienced by students as a continuous process, and the micro-level research validates the applicability of Knight's internationalisation theory. Previous studies often confined this theory to macro policies or an institutional strategy analysis (Tight, 2021), whereas this tradition is broken by this study as it is the first to demonstrate the explanatory power of internationalisation factors on individual students' micro-outcomes in the context of China. The theoretical focus is shifted in this study from the institutional input to student output, actively responding to the academic initiative proposed by De Wit and Altbach (2021) that internationalisation research should return to the essence of education and students' learning outcomes.

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